

Cyclic Acetals and Ketals of Monosaccharides. Part I. Isopropylidene-sorbose*

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Modifications of the thin-layer chromatographic method of separation of isopropylidene derivatives of monosaccharides, developed earlier by the authors¹, have led to the successful separation of the isomeric mono-*O*-isopropylidene, mono-*O*-isobutylidene, and mono-*O*-cyclohexylidene derivatives of the same sugar and helped to follow the progressive formation of the isomers 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose(II) and 2,3-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose (IV) in the acetonation of L-sorbofuranose (I) to 2, 3, 4, 6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose (III) in presence of H₂SO₄ (conc.) under various reaction conditions leading to the evidence of the formation of (III) from (II), which supports the recently proposed mechanism of formation² of (III) from (I)³.

Contrary to the observation of Okles that compound(II) cannot be further acetonated in presence of anhydrous copper sulphate, compound(III) as well as a new di-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbose from(II) have now been obtained under his conditions, their proportion decreasing as the reaction conditions are made more drastic. Formation of L-sorbofuranose also in this reaction indicates that the mechanism suggested by Tokuyama *et al.*², still holds good in part even under these mild acidic conditions.

The ring sizes of (II) and (IV) have been confirmed by periodate oxidation. A quick and convenient method of preparation of (II) has also been developed.

The process of acetonation has been extensively used for the blocking of vicinal erythro-hydroxyl groups of monosaccharides. Various catalysts, such as sulphuric acid, hydrogen chloride, phosphoric acid, *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, anhydrous zinc chloride, and anhydrous copper sulphate, have been used in this reaction. The resulting isopropylidene derivatives can be easily crystallised or distilled under reduced pressure. Stability of these derivatives under neutral and alkaline conditions make them very useful for oxidative transformations and also for preparation of partial *O*-alkyl ethers of monosaccharides. Several other ketones and aldehydes have also been used for similar blocking purposes.

An important application of the process of acetonation is the conversion of L-sorbofuranose (I) to 2,3,4,6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose (III) before oxidation to the corresponding 2-keto-L-gulonic acid in one of the commercial syntheses⁴ of vitamin C.

* Communication No. 753, National Chemical Laboratory, Poona, presented at the symposium on "Chemistry and Biochemistry of Carbohydrates" at the 2nd. Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society, at Allahabad, 1964.

1. *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 32.

2. Tokuyama *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 133.

3. *Ber.*, 1938, 71, 562.

4. Reichstein and Grüssner, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 3111.

Although acetonation of sorbose has been studied extensively by various workers, a mechanism for the transformation of pyranose (I) to furanose (III) has been put forward by Tokuyama *et al.*² only very recently. The present communication records some of our earlier observations in this field, which incidentally support this mechanism.

Acetonation of (I), catalysed by sulphuric acid, is known to provide, in addition to (III), two mono-isopropylidene-sorbofuranoses, namely, 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose (II) and 2,3-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose (IV). In attempts to improve the yield of (III), we made a detailed study of this acetonation process under various temperature conditions. The progress of the reaction was closely followed by taking small aliquots of

FIG. 1

the reaction mixture at short intervals and running their TLC (thin-layer chromatogram) after neutralisation, by the method developed by us earlier¹, which after certain modifications had later been found to effect a good separation of the isomeric (II) and (IV) as well as the isomeric mono-*O*-isobutylidene- and mono-*O*-cyclohexylidene-sorbofuranoses. Thus, the progressive formation of the three isopropylidene-sorbofuranoses (II), (III), and (IV) could be clearly followed by TLC. The results of these studies, as shown in Fig. 1-3, unequivocally establish that only (II) and (III) are formed in the initial stages of the reaction, whereas (IV) appears at a much later stage. This clearly indicates that (III) is formed from (II), a fact which has further been

confirmed by studying the acetonation of chromatographically pure (II) under the same conditions by TLC, when only (II) and (III) appear in the chromatoplates in the initial stages. Considerable amounts of (I) were also detected in these plates at all stages of this conversion.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The appearance of (IV) at a later stage in the acetonation of (I) can be ascribed to the partial hydrolysis of the more labile isopropylidene group of (III), resulting in the establishment of an equilibrium between (III) and (IV). This was also confirmed by treating chromatographically pure (III) and (IV) separately with acetic sulphuric acid, when both provided initially spots only for (II) and (IV). This incidentally confirms that (II) $\rightarrow$ (III) is an irreversible reaction. These observations therefore support the mechanism of formation of (III) as forwarded by Tokuyama *et al.*² on the basis of their kinetic studies of acetonation of (II) in which they propose the pathway as (I) $\rightarrow$ (II) $\rightarrow$ (III) $\rightarrow$ (IV), the transition (II) $\rightarrow$ (III) being postulated as through the formation of a dimer which eventually breaks up into one molecule each of (I) and (III).

By carrying out acetonation of (I) at the ordinary temperature in presence of anhydrous copper sulphate, Ohle³ found that more of (II) was formed than (III) in the reaction along with a strongly reducing substance and small quantities of a new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose, to which he did not assign any structure. We have confirmed his observations, but found by vapour-phase chromatographic (VPC) studies [Fig. 4, (2)] that almost equal quantities of (III) and the new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose are formed in this reaction. By carrying out this reaction at a higher temperature for a shorter period, as detailed in the experimental, we have been able to obtain an improved yield of (II). The proportion of (III) and the new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose, however, was found to be approximately 3:1 under these conditions [Fig. 4, (3)]. Contrary to the observation of Ohle³, that (II) cannot be further acetonated with anhydrous copper sulphate, we have been able to acetonate (II) further under these conditions. The reaction was followed by TLC. Examination of the reaction products by VPC established that (III) and the new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose were formed in almost equal quantities in this reaction also. The amount of conversion was, however, small. Sorbose was also formed in this reaction and was quantitatively estimated by the Somogyi micro-method⁵. Although the amount of

sorbose formed did not correspond to that of (III), owing probably to further acetonation of the liberated sorbose, the mechanism forwarded by Tokuyama *et al.*² still appears to be operative to some extent even under these slightly acidic conditions. The new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose probably originates from (II) without a change in the ring structure. This, however, needs further confirmation. Reaction of (I) with methyl ethyl ketone in presence of anhydrous copper sulphate similarly produced a mono-*O*-isobutylidene derivative which was in all probability analogous in structure to the 1,2-mono-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbopyranose (TLC) and two di-*O*-isobutylidene derivatives, one of which was found to be identical with the known 2, 3, 4, 6-di-*O*-isobutylidene-L-sorbofuranose (VPC) [Fig. 4 (5)].

FIG. 4. V.P.C.

The pyranose and furanose structures were assigned to (II) and (IV) respectively by Ohle³ and Reichstein and Grüssner⁴ on the basis of studies of their derivatives. We have now confirmed these structures by periodate oxidation. Two moles of periodate were consumed by (II) with liberation of about 1 mole of formic acid, whereas (IV) did not consume any periodate. This eliminates the other possible alternative structures for these compounds.

A study of the relative rates of hydrolysis of (II) and (IV) with 5% aqueous sulphuric acid was made by following the changes in optical rotation with time (Fig. 5 and 6); this showed that (II) hydrolysed nearly seven times as fast as (IV).

FIG. 5. Hydrolysis of 1,2-mono-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbopyranose at 32°.

FIG. 6. Hydrolysis of 2,3-mono-*O*-isopropylidene-L-sorbofuranose at 32°.

EXPERIMENTAL

Separation of Isomeric Isopropylidene and Allied Derivatives of Sorbose by TLC.—The original solvent system, used earlier¹ on silica gel-plaster of Paris plates, provided a small

separation of the two isomeric mono-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorboses. A much better separation of these two compounds and the corresponding mono-*O*-isobutylidene and mono-*O*-cyclohexylidene derivatives was obtained by using a solvent system consisting of a 60:40 mixture of acetone and light petroleum (40-60°). *R_f* values of these compounds and the corresponding di-derivatives are recorded in Table I. The silica gel used in these experiments was prepared in this laboratory.

TABLE I

Time of run for 10 cm. = 25 min.

Compounds.	Average <i>R_f</i> value.
1, 2- <i>O</i> -Isopropylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbopyranose ..	0.45
2, 3- <i>O</i> -Isopropylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbofuranose ..	0.58
2, 3, 4, 6-Di- <i>O</i> -isopropylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbofuranose ..	0.78
Mono- <i>O</i> -isobutylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbose [1, 2] ..	0.64
Mono- <i>O</i> -isobutylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbose [2, 3] ..	0.75
2, 3, 4, 6-Di- <i>O</i> -isobutylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbofuranose ..	0.96
Mono- <i>O</i> -cyclohexylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbose [1, 2 ?] ..	0.50
Mono- <i>O</i> -cyclohexylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbose [2, 3 ?] ..	0.64
2, 3, 4, 6-Di- <i>O</i> -cyclohexylidene- <i>L</i> -sorbofuranose ..	0.87

TLC Studies in the Progress of Acetone of Sorbose with H₂SO₄ Catalyst under Different Temp. Conditions.—The reactions were carried out under three different temperature conditions: (1) at 44°, (2) at 29°, and (3) at -8°. Anhydrous acetone (50 ml) was taken in a 250-ml three-necked r. b. flask fitted with a paraffin-seal stirrer, a thermometer, and a small dropping funnel, protected with a guard tube. H₂SO₄ (conc., 2 ml) was added dropwise and the temperature of the solution maintained at the desired level. Anhydrous sorbose (2.5 g., 250 mesh) was added and stirring continued. Aliquots (1 ml) were collected at different intervals and immediately neutralised by adding to a 17.5% solution of NaOH, cooled to -8°. The acetone solutions, separated as top layers under these conditions, were directly spotted on the TLC plates. The results are shown in Fig. 1-3. The spots near the starting point are those due to sorbose.

Similar TLC studies were also made to note the changes taking place when pure (II), (III), and (IV) were treated with acetic sulphuric acid in the same proportions at 29°. (II) was found to provide immediate spots for (III) and also prominent spots for (I), whereas (III) and (IV) showed immediate spots for (IV) and (III), respectively.

*Acetone of 1,2-*O*-Isopropylidene-*L*-sorbopyranose in presence of Anhydrous Copper Sulphate.*—Chromatographically pure anhydrous 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbopyranose (0.24 g.) was dissolved in dry acetone (25 ml) and shaken in anhydrous condition for 7 days in a microid shaker with anhydrous copper sulphate (2.5 g.) at the ordinary temperature. Copper sulphate was filtered and washed with dry acetone. The combined filtrate and washings were slightly acidic and were neutralised with a few drops of NaOH solution. The concentrate, obtained after removing acetone at the ordinary temperature by a rotary evaporator, showed spots for sorbose, the starting material, and 2,3,4,6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose in the TLC. The copper sulphate residue was found to contain traces of sorbose.

The concentrate was exhaustively extracted with dry benzene and traces of the starting material still present in the benzene extract (TLC) were removed by washing it with small quantities of dilute alkali, followed by water. The benzene solution was then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and freed of the solvent completely. The residue (0.07 g.) exhibited a single spot in TLC but VPC showed two close peaks [Fig. 4 (2)], the second being identical with that of 2,3,4,6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose. The first peak would therefore be that of the new di-*O*-isopropylidene-sorbose. The proportion of these two products was almost equal.

The benzene-insoluble residue and washings were mixed and made to 25 ml. It was found to contain sorbose and the starting material (TLC). Free sorbose was estimated in 5-ml aliquots of this solution by the Somogyi micro-method⁴ and the total quantity of sorbose was found to be 0.0025 g. The total quantity of sorbose in the copper sulphate residue was also estimated similarly and was found to be 0.0018 mg. The amount of free sorbose formed in the reaction is therefore 0.0043 g.

The total benzene residue was hydrolysed with 10*N*-H₂SO₄ (2 ml) on a boiling water bath for 15 min. and the amount of liberated sorbose was similarly estimated and found to be 0.0221 g. About half of it (c. 0.011 g.) would have resulted from 2,3,4,6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose. The amount of free sorbose liberated therefore does not fully agree with the amount required by the mechanism forwarded by Tokuyama *et al.*²

An Improved Method for the Preparation of 1,2-O-Isopropylidene-L-sorbopyranose.—Anhydrous copper sulphate (100 g.) was suspended in dry acetone (850 ml) in a three-necked r.b. flask fitted with a paraffin-seal stirrer, thermometer, and a guard tube. Pure anhydrous sorbose (10 g., 250 mesh) was then added and the mixture heated to 50° under vigorous stirring for 5 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was then filtered through two layers of filter paper and the residue washed with acetone. The slightly acidic filtrate was made alkaline by addition of 17.5% solution of NaOH (1 ml) and acetone removed at the ordinary temperature in a rotary evaporator. The resulting syrupy residue was treated with dry ether until turbid and seeded with pure 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbopyranose. After keeping in a refrigerator overnight, the crystals were filtered when the almost pure material (4.53 g.) was obtained in clusters of colorless needles; m.p. 139-41°, [α]_D²⁰ = -88.7° (water; c, 7.25). This was recrystallised from a mixture of acetone and light petroleum when a product of m.p. 142° was obtained.

The ether-benzene filtrate was freed of the solvent and the residue extracted with dry benzene. The material remaining insoluble in benzene furnished another crop of the almost pure material (0.37 g.) when crystallised from the same mixture of solvents. The total yield of the almost pure material was 4.9 g. (42.4% of theoretical).

The benzene-soluble material after washing with alkali and water and drying over sodium sulphate was freed of the solvent. The residue exhibited two peaks in the VPC corresponding to the 2,3,4,6-di-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose and the new di-*O*-isopropylidene derivative in the proportion of 3:1.

Periodate Oxidation of Mono-O-isopropylidene-sorboses.—Sodium metaperiodate (200 ml, 0.0096*N*) was added to 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbopyranose (0.626 g.), followed by a solution of sodium bicarbonate (0.05 g. in 5 ml) and the volume was made up to 250 ml.

The flask was kept in dark at the ordinary temperature. Aliquots of 20 ml were taken out at different intervals and the periodate consumption was determined by the arsenite method. The results are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Time.	0.01 <i>N</i> -Arsenite consumed.	IO ₄ ⁻ consumed.	Time.	0.01 <i>N</i> -Arsenite consumed.	IO ₄ ⁻ consumed.
0.5 hr.	0.55	0.24 <i>M</i>	3.0 hr.	2.00	1.14 <i>M</i>
1.0	1.05	0.47	3.5	2.80	1.23
1.5	1.55	0.69	4.0	3.15	1.30
2.0	1.85	0.83	6.0	3.65	1.71
2.5	2.30	1.00	9.0	4.85	2.15
			21.0	6.20	2.74

Erroneous results were obtained if sodium bicarbonate was not added to the reaction mixture, probably because of the lability of the isopropylidene derivative in presence of acids (liberated formic acid).

2,3-*O*-Isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose did not consume any periodate even after 48 hr.

For determination of acidity, 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose (0.265 g.) was treated with sodium metaperiodate (200 ml, 0.01*N*) and the solution was kept in dark. The acidity was determined by titrating an aliquot after 18 hr. with 0.01*N*-NaOH solution, using Methyl red as indicator, and was found to be 0.05*M*. The low value possibly resulted from side reactions.

Vapour phase Chromatographic Studies of Di-O-isopropylidene- and Di-O-isobutylidene-sorboses.—The VPC studies were made with an aerograph, model A-350B instrument, using a silicone grease column heated at 250°. Hydrogen was used as the carrier gas. The retention time of these derivatives was found to be very short under these conditions.

Studies in the Change of Rotation of the two Mono-O-isopropylidene-sorboses with 5% Aqueous H₂SO₄.—The rotations were taken at 32° with a Perkin Elmer automatic polarimeter, model 141, at $\lambda=589$ Å. The concentration of 1,2-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose was 0.0149 g./ml and that of 2, 3-*O*-isopropylidene-*L*-sorbofuranose was 0.0145 g./ml. The relative rates of hydrolysis of the two products were calculated from the data obtained from various points on these curves.

The authors are thankful to Dr. V. G. Naik of this laboratory for his help in the VPC studies.